

Formation and Reproportionation Constants of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Lanthanion Ions with Nitrilotriacetic Acid and β -isopropyltropolone

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1:1:1 mixed ligand complexes of La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Yb(III) and Y(III) with nitrilotriacetic acid and β -isopropyltropolone (β T) have been studied potentiometrically in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan medium at 0.1M NaClO₄ ionic concentration and 30 \pm 1°. The formation constants have been calculated by weighted least squares method. Reproportionation constant, which gives the idea about the compatibility of various ligands in the coordination sphere of a given metal ion, have also been calculated. The results of present investigation show that nitrilotriacetic acid and β -isopropyltropolone are incompatible ligands and the mixed ligand complexes are less stable than either of the parent complexes formed by the same ligands.

FORMATION and reproportionation constants of mixed ligand complexes of lanthanons using nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as primary ligand and tropolone as secondary ligand, have already been reported¹. Mixed ligand complexes of bivalent metal ions with tropolones as secondary ligands while dipyriddy and phenanthroline as primary ligands have also been studied^{2,3}. In the present communication, the results of potentiometric investigations on mixed ligand complexes of lanthanion ions using nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as primary ligand and β -isopropyltropolone (β T) as secondary ligand, have been discussed. The work has been extended to study the compatibility of these ligands in the coordination sphere of the metal ions and it has been observed that the stability of the mixed ligand complex formed is related to the stability of the binary complexes formed by same ligands.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents: A Beckman pH meter SS-2 model, with glass electrode and reference calomel electrode was used for pH-measurements. The gradual addition of alkali during titrations was done with the help of capillary nozzle. All metal ion solutions were prepared from A. R. lanthanion nitrate samples obtained from Indian Rare Earth Ltd, and their solutions were standardised by gravimetric method and complexometric method using xylenol orange as indicator. Nitrilotriacetic acid (Riedel) was dissolved in 3 equivalents of NaOH solution and was used as trisodium salt. β -Iso-propyltropolone (Koch-Light) was dissolved in freshly distilled dioxan, while tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck) was dissolved in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan and its solution was standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate. Dioxan was purified by refluxing with sodium wire for 24 hours and

was freshly distilled over sodium before use. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Presaturated nitrogen with (50% v/v aqueous dioxan) was passed through the solutions during titrations. The titration vessel was maintained at 30 \pm 1° with the help of thermostat. The following solutions (total volume 19.7 ml due to contraction in volume on mixing dioxan) were titrated against 0.05M TMAH solution.

- (i) 3.0 ml HC O₄ (0.02M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0M) + 0.5ml NaNO₃ (0.02M) + 5.5 ml water + 10.0 ml dioxan.
- (ii) 3.0 ml. HClO₄ (0.02M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0M) + 0.5 ml NaNO₃ (0.02M) + 0.5 ml NTA (0.02M) + 5.0 ml water + 10.0 ml dioxan.
- (iii) 3.0 ml HClO₄ (0.2M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0M) + 0.5 ml NaNO₃ (0.02M) + 0.5 ml sec ligand (0.02M) + 5.5 ml water + 9.5 ml dioxan.
- (iv) 3.0 ml HClO₄[±] (0.02M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0M) + 0.5 ml NTA (0.02M) + 0.5 ml metal ion (0.02M) + 5.0 ml water + 10.0 ml dioxan.
- (v) 3.0 ml HClO₄ (0.02M) + 1.0 ml NaClO₄ (2.0M) + 0.5 ml NTA (0.02M) + 0.5 ml metal ion (0.02M) + 0.5 ml sec ligand (0.02M) + 5.0 ml water + 9.5 ml dioxan.

Results and Discussion

The proton ligand stability constant for β T and the formation constants for the following equilibria have been calculated as described in our earlier publication¹⁻⁴.

NTA reacts with lanthanon ions at lower pH which is evident from the titration curve of solution (iv). It has also been observed that titration curves for solutions (iv) and (v) overlap in lower pH range thereby showing that βT does not coordinate in this pH range. At higher pH (> 4.5) the divergence of curves for solution (iv) and (v) shows the coordination of βT with the species $[M - NTA]$. Thus the formation constant of the mixed ligand complex may be given by

$$\beta_{1,1} = \frac{[\beta T - M - NTA]}{[M - NTA][\beta T]}$$

The formation constants for NTA and βT binary complexes have been redetermined under present set of conditions and are in good agreement with earlier reported values⁵. \bar{n} and pL values have been calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁶ and these values have been utilized for the computation of formation constants by weighted least squares method⁷. The β_n values were first approximated from (\bar{n} , pL) data with weight factor being unity. Second approximations to the β_n values were then calculated by attaching to them appropriate weight factors, computed from first set of β_n values. This process was repeated till successive cycles produced a change of less than one part per thousand in each β_n values. The consistency of the resulting parameters, measurements and the esteemed errors associated with measurements are tested by calculating the values of $S_{m \pm n}$, which have the same significance as χ^2 , with k degrees of freedom⁸.

Reproportionation constant (K_a) correlates the relative stability of mixed ligand complex with those of the parent complexes formed using same ligands. The correlation between the formation constants and reproportionation constant is given by the following relation :

$$K_a = \frac{\beta_{i,j}}{\beta_{m,0}^{i/m} \cdot \beta_{0,m}^{j/m}} \quad (\text{where } i + j = m)$$

According to this equation, formation constant of the mixed ligand complex is directly proportional to the geometric mean of the formation constants of the parent complexes and the proportionality factor is reproportionation constant. Reproportionation constant gives the measure of the compatibility of different ligands in the coordination sphere of a given metal ion. If the ligands are incompatible, then the mixed ligand complex formed will be less stable than either of the parent complexes and the reproportionation constant will be less than one⁹. Results of these investigations are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES OF LANTHANONS WITH β -ISOPROPYL TROPOLONE AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$, CALCULATED BY BJERRUM'S HALF INTEGRAL METHOD

Metal ion	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	log K_3	log β_3
H ⁺	7.92	—	—	—	—
La(III)	7.46	6.04	13.50	3.82	17.32
Pr(III)	7.54	6.31	13.85	4.68	18.53
Nd(III)	7.64	6.60	14.24	5.08	19.32
Sm(III)	7.78	7.22	15.00	5.62	20.62
Gd(III)	7.74	6.75	14.49	5.05	19.54
Dy(III)	7.90	7.58	15.48	6.08	21.56
Yb(III)	8.20	7.75	15.95	6.53	22.48
Y(III)	7.85	7.43	15.28	5.95	21.23

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES OF LANTHANONS WITH β -ISOPROPYL TROPOLONE AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$, CALCULATED BY WEIGHTED LEAST SQUARES METHOD

Metal ion	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	log K_3	log β_3	$S_{m \pm n}$
La(III)	7.12	5.82	12.94	3.85	15.79	0.1286
Pr(III)	7.28	5.98	13.26	4.51	17.77	0.0015
Nd(III)	7.42	6.10	13.52	4.51	18.03	0.0186
Sm(III)	7.53	6.18	13.71	4.65	18.36	0.0211
Gd(III)	7.48	6.20	13.68	5.10	18.78	0.0176
Dy(III)	7.64	6.29	13.93	5.40	19.33	0.0158
Yb(III)	7.85	6.32	14.17	5.58	19.75	0.1215
Y(III)	7.70	6.29	13.97	5.31	19.30	0.1007

TABLE 3—FORMATION AND REPROPORTIONATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF LANTHANONS WITH β -ISOPROPYL TROPOLONE AND NITRILOTRIACETIC ACID AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$

Metal ion	$\beta_{1,1}$	$S_{m \pm n}$	K_a
La(III)	1.26×10^5	0.524	6.20×10^{-11}
Pr(III)	2.75×10^5	0.229	2.04×10^{-11}
Nd(III)	7.41×10^5	0.027	1.72×10^{-11}
Sm(III)	1.23×10^6	0.056	0.94×10^{-11}
Gd(III)	2.04×10^6	0.125	1.17×10^{-11}
Dy(III)	3.71×10^6	0.090	1.06×10^{-11}
Yb(III)	6.92×10^6	1.897	0.76×10^{-11}
Y(III)	2.57×10^6	0.203	0.35×10^{-11}

Present investigations reveal that :

(i) mixed ligand complexes are less stable than either of the parent complexes formed by the same ligands. Although the entropy effect always favours the formation of mixed ligand complex, but the steric hindrance created by bulky NTA molecule for the incoming β T anion, reduces the stability of the mixed species considerably. Also, the electrostatic force of attraction between $[M\text{-NTA}]$ and β T should be less than that of β T with $[M(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{3+}$.

(ii) The values of $\beta_{1,1}$ for the mixed ligand complexes are found to be greater than $\beta_{0,2}$ for binary complexes. It is quite evident, because in the formation of ML_2 species with NTA the coulombic repulsion forces are greater. The formation of species $[\beta\text{T-M-NTA}]^-$ is always preferred over the formation of $[M\text{-(NTA)}_2]^{3-}$ or $[M\text{-(}\beta\text{T)}_2]^{+}$.

(iii) The formation constants of mixed ligand complexes of tropolone¹ have lower values as compared to those formed by β -isopropyltropolone using NTA as primary ligand. This is in good agreement with the pK values of these ligands.

(iv) The values of reproportionation constant is less than one in all the cases. This shows that NTA and β T are incompatible ligands in the coordination sphere of lanthanon ions. Also, these values are quite close to one another (Table 3), which indicates that all the lanthanon ions behave in the same manner towards these two ligands. This may be due to the differences in the structures and the bond types of the parent complexes formed by these two ligands^{10,11}. In such cases, the bond between the metal ion and one of the ligands become more ionic and that between the metal ion and the other ligand becomes more covalent. These effects are of opposite sign and the net energy change may be either positive or negative depending upon the nature of species involved¹².

(v) The parallel change in the reproportionation constants and formation constants is not general. In the present studies also, it has been noticed that reproportionation constant does not vary linearly with formation constants. Although, the value of formation constant increases from lanthanum to ytterbium but at the same time the value of reproportionation constant decreases in disordered manner. In general, it can be concluded that these values depend upon the number, nature of the coordinating ligands and their mutual interactions present in the coordination sphere of the given metal ion. At the same time, the properties of metal ion such as ionic radii, also have their major role in deciding the compatibility of the ligands.

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